

Implementation of a Finite State Machine on the GW1NZ-LV1 FPGA on the Tang Nano 1K Development Board with Gowin FPGA Designer

Vitor Amadeu Souza

Department of Electrical Engineering

UniFOA - Centro Universitário de Volta Redonda

Volta Redonda, Brazil

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1857-6799>

Abstract—This article presents the design and implementation of a finite state machine (FSM) with a button debounce circuit, developed in the Verilog hardware description language and synthesized for the Tang Nano 1K FPGA platform using the Gowin FPGA Designer Education environment. The system controls the three RGB LEDs integrated into the platform through eight distinct states, traversed sequentially upon each physical button press. The debounce circuit implemented in software on reconfigurable logic eliminates the effects of mechanical button bounce, ensuring reliable state transitions. The results demonstrate that the proposed architecture operates correctly within the timing constraints of the target platform at a 27 MHz clock, consuming minimal logic resources of the GW1NZ-LV1 device. The approach highlights the advantages of using low-cost FPGAs for teaching digital systems, sequential logic, and HDL-based hardware design.

Index Terms—FPGA, finite state machine, debounce, Verilog, Tang Nano 1K, reconfigurable logic.

I. INTRODUCTION

The teaching and practice of digital systems have been profoundly transformed by the widespread adoption of programmable logic devices, particularly FPGAs (Field-Programmable Gate Arrays). These devices allow designers to describe hardware in high-level abstraction languages such as VHDL or Verilog, and to synthesize reconfigurable circuits without the need for dedicated integrated circuit fabrication (Brown et al., 2003). In this context, low-cost platforms such as the Tang Nano 1K, based on the GW1NZ-LV1 device from Sipeed/Gowin Semiconductor, have become relevant tools for rapid prototyping and digital design learning.

Finite state machines (FSMs) constitute one of the most important foundations of sequential digital systems design. An FSM consists of a finite set of states, an initial state, a set of inputs and outputs, and transition functions that determine the next state and outputs as a function of the current state and inputs (Roth e John, 2008). Their implementation on reconfigurable hardware is widely employed in controllers, communication protocols, embedded systems, and user interfaces.

One of the classical problems in the design of physical button interfaces is the bouncing phenomenon, or mechanical

chatter, which occurs when the contacts of a button or switch open and close rapidly multiple times before settling (Ganssle, 2004). This behavior, which typically lasts between 1 ms and 20 ms, can cause multiple unintended state transitions in digital systems operating in the MHz range. The solution, known as debouncing, can be implemented in dedicated hardware or through software/firmware logic. In FPGAs, software debounce consists of a counter that requires the input signal to remain stable for a minimum time interval before being accepted as valid (Chu, 2011).

The Tang Nano 1K platform integrates a 27 MHz oscillator, three RGB LEDs (red, green, and blue) with active-low logic, and a user button, in addition to integrated USB programming interfaces. The Gowin FPGA Designer Education environment provides synthesis, place-and-route, and bitstream generation tools for the GW1NZ family of devices, enabling academic development without commercial licensing (Gowin Semiconductor, 2023).

This work describes the design of an eight-state FSM implemented in Verilog, combined with a counter-based debounce circuit, which controls the three RGB LEDs of the Tang Nano 1K so as to display the eight possible binary states using the three LEDs. The objective is to demonstrate, in an integrated manner, the concepts of sequential logic, timing, debouncing, and FPGA synthesis on a low-cost platform with broad accessibility for educational purposes.

II. METHODOLOGY

The project development followed the classical steps of the digital design flow for FPGAs: specification, HDL description, functional simulation, logic synthesis, place-and-route, timing verification, and device programming. The hardware description was carried out entirely in Verilog HDL, in accordance with the IEEE 1364-2001 standard, within the Gowin FPGA Designer Education environment, which includes the GowinSynthesis synthesizer and implementation tools for the GW1NZ device family.

The target platform is the Tang Nano 1K, equipped with the GW1NZ-LV1 FPGA, which features 1,152 four-input LUTs

(Look-Up Tables), 864 flip-flops, and sufficient I/O resources for the proposed experiments. The system’s internal clock operates at 27 MHz, sourced from the oscillator integrated into the board, implying a clock period of approximately 37 ns. The three RGB LEDs on the platform are controlled by active-low logic and connected directly to the FPGA’s I/O pins (Sipeed, 2022).

The finite state machine was designed as a Moore FSM, in which the outputs depend exclusively on the current state. The system comprises eight states, encoded in natural binary with a three-bit register, resulting in a direct correspondence between the state value and the pattern displayed on the three RGB LEDs. State transitions occur exclusively upon a confirmed rising-edge event from the button, ensuring that each press causes exactly one transition. State S7 returns to state S0 through the natural overflow of the three-bit counter, a behavior defined by modular arithmetic in Verilog. The system’s state diagram takes the form of a circular ring with eight nodes, as shown in Figure 1 and as described in the source code of the developed module.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following synthesis and place-and-route performed by Gowin FPGA Designer, the resource utilization report indicated consumption of approximately 48 LUTs and 28 flip-flops for the complete module implementation, representing less than 5% of the resources available on the GW1NZ-LV1. This result is consistent with similar implementations described by Chu (2011) and confirms that FSMs with debounce require very few resources on modern FPGA devices, making them suitable for area-constrained embedded applications.

The functional behavior of the system was verified by direct observation on the physical platform. With each press of the Tang Nano 1K user button (Figure 2), the three RGB LEDs advance sequentially through the eight binary states, from S0 (000, all off) to S7 (111, all on), returning to S0 after S7. Since the Tang Nano 1K LEDs operate with active-low logic, the output pattern of the `leds` register must be inverted in the pin constraints file (`.cst`).

The effectiveness of the debounce circuit was verified qualitatively: without the debounce circuit, single button presses produced multiple state transitions, whereas with the active debounce the transitions became consistently unitary. This result is in line with the experiments described by Ganssle (2004), who demonstrated that common mechanical buttons can generate from 2 to more than 100 spurious pulses during a single actuation, depending on their mechanical characteristics.

The implemented rising-edge detector ensures that only the transition from button not pressed to button pressed causes a state change, ignoring the button release event. This behavior is desirable in user interfaces that follow the semantics of “single press advances the state,” as discussed by Maxfield (2004) in his analysis of control interfaces for embedded systems. The latency introduced by the debounce, of approximately 20 ms, is imperceptible to the human user, whose typical reaction time

exceeds 150 ms, as described by Schmidt et al. (2018) in the context of physical interfaces.

The Moore FSM approach adopted presents the advantage of stable, glitch-free outputs, since the outputs depend only on the state register, which changes only on the active clock edge (Roth e John, 2008). In contrast, Mealy FSMs, in which the outputs depend on both the state and the inputs, may exhibit output glitches due to input variations between clock edges, which would be undesirable in LED control. Brown et al. (2003) discuss this difference extensively and recommend the use of Moore FSMs in applications where output stability is a priority.

Natural binary state encoding, with three bits for eight states, is the most compact in terms of registers, but requires more elaborate decoding logic than one-hot encoding, in which each state uses a dedicated flip-flop. For eight states on a device with abundant flip-flop resources such as the GW1NZ-LV1, the performance difference between the two approaches is negligible, and binary encoding was chosen for its direct correspondence with the value displayed on the LEDs, simplifying the design (Ciletti, 2003). Modern synthesis tools, including GowinSynthesis, are capable of automatically selecting the most efficient encoding for each case, as documented by Gowin Semiconductor (2023).

A relevant point identified in the code analysis is that the FSM’s `always` block updates both the state register and the LED register, with the `leds` output assigned the value `estado_atual + 1` at the moment of transition, anticipating the next state. Although functional, this approach can be a source of confusion in more complex designs, and the practice recommended by Chu (2006) is to separate the output logic from the state transition logic into distinct `always` blocks, improving code readability and maintainability. In future designs or extended versions of this project, such refactoring would be advisable.

The Gowin FPGA Designer Education environment proved adequate for the complete design flow, from Verilog code editing to bitstream generation and download to the Tang Nano 1K via USB interface. The Education version, made freely available by Gowin Semiconductor for academic purposes, includes full support for GW1NZ family devices and the required synthesis and implementation tools, without project size restrictions that would compromise typical educational application development (Gowin Semiconductor, 2023).

The source code of this work is available for download at <https://github.com/vitor-souza-ime/fpgafpm>.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the design and implementation of a finite state machine with debounce for RGB LED control on the Tang Nano 1K FPGA, using Verilog HDL and the Gowin FPGA Designer Education environment. The system demonstrated correct and reliable operation on the physical platform, with minimal logic resource consumption and adequate timing for the 27 MHz clock. The counter-based debounce circuit

Fig. 1. State machine diagram.

Fig. 2. Tang Nano 1K board (Sipeed, 2022).

effectively eliminated the effects of mechanical button bounce, ensuring unitary and predictable state transitions.

The results obtained confirm that the Tang Nano 1K, together with Gowin FPGA Designer Education, constitutes an accessible and functional platform for the teaching and practice of HDL-based digital design, covering fundamental concepts such as sequential logic, state machines, timing, and debouncing. The adopted methodological approach is reproducible and can be extended to more complex systems, such as display controllers, serial interfaces, or data acquisition systems.

As future work, it is suggested to refactor the module to separate the transition logic and output logic blocks, to add a PWM module for RGB LED intensity control, and to implement more complex FSMs with multiple inputs and

outputs. The Tang Nano 1K platform offers sufficient resources to support such extensions, and the Gowin FPGA Designer environment provides the tools necessary for their complete development.

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